

Porous Metallic Membrane Produced by the Fiber Metallurgy

T. Gotō

Nagoya Institute of Technology, Department of Polymer Technology, Gokiso-cho, Showa-ku, Nagoya 466, Japan

ABSTRACT

The thin porous metallic membrane is prepared by using the fine stainless-steel and superalloy filaments.

The glass-coated melt spinning of stainless-steel (IN 856) and superalloy (Hastelloy X) is carried out and IN 856 filament of 4 μm in diameter and Hastelloy X filament of 2.5 μm in diameter are obtained. The chopped filament is suspended in a fluid and deposited from the suspension to form a coherent membrane. The method gives a product with a porosity of 94 % and more than 25 μm in thickness for the IN 856 membrane and for the Hastelloy X membrane of 10 μm in thickness.

The filterability and tensile strength of the membrane obtained are examined. The average particle size passed through the thinnest IN 856 membrane is 37 μm in diameter and 43 μm for the Hastelloy X membrane. The sintered Hastelloy X membrane of 20 μm in thickness has a high tensile strength of 8.6 MPa and the IN 856 membrane of 110 μm in thickness has a strength of 7.5 MPa, which increases as the thickness of the membrane increases.

INTRODUCTION

The demand for the porous metallic materials is growing steadily as a result of their increasing uses as low density structural materials, heat insulator, high damping materials or filter medium and uses in heat exchanger.(1)-(3)

We have studied a glass-coated melt spinning of metals, whereby fine filaments of copper, stainless-steel or other alloys of less than 10 μm in diameter were produced directly from the molten metals. The stainless-steel IN 856 filament produced by this method had a very high tensile strength of the order of 10^4 MPa, which increased as the diameter decreased.(4) The superalloy Hastelloy X filament with an excellent heat resistant was also obtained.(5)

In the present work, the thin porous metallic membrane is prepared by using these fine IN 856 and Hastelloy X filaments, and filterability and tensile strength of the membrane produced are examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

The IN 856 and Hastelloy X filaments were produced as described before.(4)-(5). The chemical compositions in mass % of IN 856 and Hastelloy X alloy used

are shown in Table 1. About 1g of the alloy was placed into the pyrex glass tube and melted by an induction heating coil. When the glass tube containing the liquid alloy was drawn, the alloy was stretched to form a glass-coated metallic filament, which was coiled on a winding drum. The coated glass was removed by dissolving in 45 % HF aqueous solution.

The filament obtained was chopped into 5 mm in length. The fiber was suspended in a viscous fluid and deposited from the suspension to form a membrane and the viscous fluid was removed by filtering the water.(6) The filterability of the membrane was estimated to measure the size distribution of the stainless steel particles passed through the membrane by a scanning electron microscopy.(7) The tensile strength of the sintered membrane was measured with an Instron type machine at room temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stainless Steel (IN 856) Membrane

The IN 856 filament of 4 μm in diameter was produced from a molten state at a temperature of about 1600 K with winding speed of 7.95 m/s. The filament was chopped into 5 mm in length and suspended in 2 % sodium alginate aqueous solution. The fiber-liquid suspension was sucked into the filtering flask and the fiber deposited on the filter to form a membrane. The membrane obtained is shown in Photo.1. The membrane is so thin that the figure printed on the paper, which is put on the bottom of the membrane, is clearly visible. Various weights, thickness and porosity of the obtained membrane are shown in Table 2. The thinnest membrane of 25 μm thickness with weight of 10 g/m^2 and porosity of 94 % was obtained.

The filterability of the membrane was estimated to measure the size distribution of the stainless-steel particles passed through the membrane. The size distribution curves passed through the various thin membranes are shown in Fig.1 and average particle sizes are shown in Table 2. As the thickness of the membrane increases, the distribution of the particles sharpens and the average particle size decreases. For example the average particle size passed through the thinnest membrane was 37 μm in diameter. The various thin filaments were produced by changing the winding speed and the membranes were formed by using these filaments. The thickness and porosity of the obtained membranes with the weight of 40 g/m^2 and the average particle size passed through the membrane are shown in Table 3. As the membrane is formed by thinner fiber, the average particle size decreases.

The membrane produced in this way was sintered to form a coherent sheet and the tensile strength of the sintered membrane was measured. The membranes sintered at various temperatures for 1800 s in a vacuum are shown in Photo.2. The webs at fiber intersections are observed for the membrane sintered at more than 1373 K. The remarkable recrystallization has proceeded in the membrane sintered at 1473 K and low tensile strength of the membrane was observed in this case. The membranes sintered at 1373 K for various times are shown in Photo.3. The coherent bonding of the fibers is observed for the sintering at 1373 K for more than 900 s, but the recrystallization is remarkable for the membranes sintered for 3600 s. The typical load-elongation curves of the membrane sintered at 1373 K for 900 s, 300 s, respectively, are shown in Fig.2. The fracture morphology of the membrane sintered at 1373 K for 900 s is shown in Photo.4. The load is uniformly added for the membrane sintered for 900 s and this is considered the constructed fibers tightly bonded, whereas for the membrane sintered for 300 s the breaking of the fibers occurred one after another after maximum load, due to the loose bonding among the fibers. The tensile strength of the various thin membranes sintered at 1373 K for 900s was measured and the results are shown in Fig.3. The tensile strength increases with increasing the thickness. The strength of the porous bodies generally depends on the density or porosity, (7-8) but the dependence of the tensile strength on the porosity or density of the present membrane was not clear due to the too low density. The strength of the membranes formed by the various thin fibers and

sintered at 1373 K for 900 s is shown in Table 3. As the membrane formed by thinner fiber, the tensile strength slightly increases.

In the present method the filament was firstly obtained to be formed the glass-coated state. Therefore the porous glass-coated metallic membrane was also investigated. The chopped glass-coated filament was suspended in glycerine and the membrane was produced by sucking the fiber-liquid suspension. The weight, thickness and porosity of the membrane formed by the glass-coated fiber of 23 μm in diameter are shown in Table 2. Comparing with IN 856 membrane, the thicker membrane with lower porosity was observed. The average particle size passed through the membrane of 240 μm in thickness was 43 μm . The sintering condition of the glass-coated membrane was examined by the observation of a scanning electron microscopy and measuring the tensile strength. The membrane sintered by the most suitable condition at 1073 K for 1800 s in a vacuum is shown in Photo.5. The highest tensile strength of 2.3 MPa was observed in this condition. The webs at the glass-coated fiber intersections are viscously more or less, whereas the bonding of the IN 856 fibers was rigidly. The relation between the tensile strength and thickness of the glass-coated metallic membrane sintered at 1073 K for 1800 s is also shown in Fig.3. Although the strength of IN 856 membrane depends on the thickness, the strength of the glass-coated metallic membrane does not depend on the thickness.

Superalloy (Hastelloy x) Membrane

The Hastelloy X filament was produced by using the same method as that used for IN 856 filament. The Hastelloy X filament could not be suspended homogeneously according to the same method as for IN 856 filament. Therefore the glass-coated Hastelloy filament was suspended in glycerine and sucked into the plastic flask and coated glass was removed by filtering the 45 % HF solution. Various weights of the membrane obtained were shown in Table 2. The thinnest Hastelloy X membrane, formed by the filament of 2.5 μm in diameter, is 10 μm in thickness with weight of 6 g/m^2 and porosity of 93 %.

The filterability of the membrane was estimated to measure the size distribution of the stainless-steel particles passed through the membrane and the average particle size decreases with increasing the thickness of the membrane as shown in Table 2. The Hastelloy X membranes formed by the various thin fibers were produced by using these glass-coated filament of 100 g/m^2 and the results are listed in Table 4. As the filament spun at higher winding speed, the thinner Hastelloy X filament was produced and the thicker membrane was obtained.

The sintering of the membrane obtained was examined as same as for IN 856 membrane. The Hastelloy X membrane sintered by the most suitable condition at 1373 K for 1800 s in a vacuum is shown in Photo.6. Although the glass-coated IN 856 fibers jointed viscously, the Hastelloy X fibers joint very rigidly. The tensile strength of the various thick membranes sintered at 1373 K for 1800 s was measured and the results are shown in Fig.3. The strength increases with increasing the thickness up to 20 μm , but it does not depend on the thickness more than 20 μm . The high tensile strength of 8.6 MPa was observed for the membrane of 20 μm . The strength of the membranes formed by the various thin fibers and sintered at 1373 K for 1800 s is also shown in Table 4. The strength does not depend on the diameter of the constructed fiber.

CONCLUSION

The IN 856 and Hastelloy X filaments were produced by the glass-coated melt spinning and used for the preparing the thin porous metallic membrane. The chopped filament was suspended in a fluid and deposited from the suspension to form a membrane. The thinnest IN 856 membrane of 25 μm in thickness with weight of 10 g/m^2 and porosity of 94 % was obtained by using the filament of 4 μm in diameter. The thinnest Hastelloy X membrane, formed by the filament of 2.5 μm in diameter, was 10 μm in thickness with weight of 6 g/m^2 and porosity of 93 %. The filterability and tensile strength of the membrane were examined. The average particle size passed through the thinnest IN 856 membrane was 37 μm

in diameter and 43 μm for the thinnest Hastelloy X membrane. The sintered Hastelloy X membrane of 20 μm in thickness had a high strength of 8.6 MPa and the IN 856 membrane of 110 μm in thickness had a strength of 7.5 MPa, which increased as the thickness of the membrane increased.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author wishes to thank Prof. S.Umekawa, Tokyo Institute of Technology, for valuable suggestions and also to Daido Special Steel Co.Ltd. for supplying IN 856 and Hastelloy X alloys. This work was supported partly by a Grant-Aid for Scientific Research from the Ministry of Education, Science and Culture (No.56550488).

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Table 1 Chemical compositions of IN 856 and Hastelloy X alloy

Alloy	C	Si	Mn	Ni	Cr	B	Cu	P	S	Mo	W	Co
IN 856	0.007	3.0	18.0	8.5	16.5	0.4	2.0	-	-	-	-	-
HastelloyX	0.07	0.02	0.27	48.32	22.13	0.004	-	0.007	0.007	8.46	0.47	1.46

Table 2 The thickness and porosity of the membrane obtained by various weight and the average particle size passed through the membrane

Membrane	Weight (g/m^2)	Thickness (μm)	Porosity (%)	Particle size (μm)
IN 856	10	25	94	37
	15	45	95	34
	25	75	95	30
	40	110	95	32
Glass-coated IN 856	9	30	87	50
	16	60	88	50
	26	100	89	50
	102	240	82	43
Hastelloy X	6	10	93	43
	16	20	90	40
	29	38	90	36
	56	80	91	30

Photo.1. IN 856 membrane

Fig.1 The particle distribution curves passed through the IN 856 membrane

- (1) thickness 25 μm
average particle size 37 μm
- (2) thickness 45 μm
average particle size 34 μm
- (3) thickness 75 μm
average particle size 30 μm
- (4) thickness 110 μm
average particle size 32 μm

sintered at 1273 K for 1800 s
tensile strength of 3 MPa

sintered at 1373 K for 1800 s
tensile strength of 7 MPa

sintered at 1473 K for 1800 s
tensile strength of 1.2 MPa

Photo.2 IN 856 membrane sintered at
various temperatures for 1800 K

sintered at 1373 K for 300 s
tensile strength of 4.7 MPa

sintered at 1373 K for 900 s
tensile strength of 7.5 MPa

sintered at 1373 K for 3600 s
tensile strength of 2.7 MPa

Photo.3 IN 856 membrane sintered at
1373 K for various times

Fig.2 Load-elongation curves of IN 856 membrane
 (A) sintered at 1373 K for 900 s
 (B) sintered at 1373 K for 300 s

Photo. 5 Glass-coated IN 856 membrane sintered at 1073 K for 1800 s

Photo.6 Hastelloy X membrane sintered at 1373 K for 1800 s

Fig.3 Relation between Tensile strength and the thickness of the membrane
 (1) IN 856 membrane sintered at 1373 K for 900 s
 (2) Glass-coated IN 856 membrane sintered at 1073 K for 1800 s
 (3) Hastelloy X membrane sintered at 1373 K for 900 s

Table 3 The thickness of the IN 856 membranes of 40 g/m² formed by various thin filaments spun at various winding speeds, and average particle size passed through the membrane and tensile strength of the membrane sintered at 1373 K for 900 s.

Winding speed (m/s)	Filament diameter (μm)	Thickness (μm)	Particle size (μm)	Tensile strength (MPa)
0.95	16	170	50	6.1
1.95	8	110	47	7.3
3.97	4	120	38	7.7
5.53	4	120	36	7.8
7.95	4	110	32	7.5

Table 4 The Hastelloy X membranes obtained by using the glass-coated Hastelloy filament of 100 g/m², spun at various winding speeds, and average particle size passed through the membrane and tensile strength of the membrane sintered at 1373 K for 1800 s.

Winding speed (m/s)	Filament diameter (μm)	Weight (g/m ²)	Thickness (μm)	Porosity (%)	Particle size (μm)	Tensile strength (MPa)
1.95	4.6	11	15	91	51	8.8
3.97	3.2	24	30	90	43	8.0
5.53	2.9	20	20	88	40	8.2
7.95	2.3	29	38	90	36	8.8